

Iris Claw Intraocular Lens Implantation as a Primary or Secondary Procedure- A Study Done at a Tertiary Care CentreJemi Sandhyavali Lam¹, Harika Mada², Sivaramprasad Vontipulli³, Syed Salma Sultana⁴¹Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur⁴Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Jemi Sandhyavali Lam

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Abstract:

Purpose: cataract is the leading cause of reversible blindness in the world. Aphakia due to complicated cataract surgery is difficult to treat with spectacles or contact lenses. Implantation of iris claw intraocular lens (ICIOL) is one of the various methods. This study aims to evaluate the visual acuity and post-operative complications after implantation of iris claw intraocular lens as a primary or secondary procedure.

Methods: This is a retrospective study conducted at government general hospital, Guntur from May 1st 2023 to April 30th 2024. Data from 50 eyes of 49 patients was collected from records. Their preoperative evaluation, intraoperative approach as a primary or secondary procedure and postoperative visual acuity and complications were noted. All patients were followed-up for a period of 6 weeks.

Results: The study includes a total of 49 patients of which 26 are males and 23 Females with mean age of 56-60. Among the 50 eyes 27 were right with 23 left eyes. Four patients had ICIOL implantation as a primary procedure and 45 as a secondary procedure. Indications for surgery include posterior capsule rupture in 42 patients and zonular dehiscence in 8 patients. Postoperative vision improved to 6/12 to 6/9 in majority of patients at the end of 6 weeks. Complications like striate keratopathy seen in 26 patients, horizontal oval pupil in 32, and cystoid macular oedema in 2 and suprachoroidal haemorrhage in 1 patient.

Conclusion: Iris claw intraocular lens implantation can be done in eyes with complicated cataract surgery with inadequate posterior capsular support. It gives patients good visual acuity postoperatively with fewer complications.

Keywords: Iris claw lens, Retro-pupillary iris claw, aphakia, cataract, posterior capsule rupture, zonular dehiscence.

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Introduction

Cataract is the most common cause of blindness in the world. It consists of opacification of clear lens fibres which impairs the passage of light. Its global prevalence is 15.2 million people who became blind and 78.8 million people became visually impaired.[1] Removal of cataractous lens and replacing with posterior chamber intraocular lens provides excellent visual rehabilitation. Posterior capsular rupture is one of the complications of cataract surgery; it is seen to occur in 0.45% to 5.2% of cases.[1] Inadequate posterior capsular support makes it difficult to implant posterior chamber IOL leading to aphakia.

Aphakic patients present with high hypermetropia and astigmatism. Insufficient posterior capsular or ciliary zonular support makes it difficult to implant conventional posterior chamber intraocular lens.

Options available for the surgeon to correct aphakia are glasses, contact lens, kerato-refractive surgery and intraocular lens (IOL).[2] The various IOLs available are anterior chamber IOL (ACIOL), scleral fixated IOL and anterior and posterior iris fixated IOL. Eye's status and surgeons experience play a significant role in choosing the procedure of choice.

IOL sizing is the major drawback of ACIOL, smaller diameter IOL causes rotation and dislocation leading to increased damage to corneal endothelium and anterior chamber angle. Large diameter IOL causes peripheral anterior synechiae, raised intraocular pressure and glaucoma. [3]Scleral fixated IOL has main advantages like the more physiological location and increased distance from corneal, which decreases risk of corneal

endothelial decompensation. However, in scleral fixation the surgery is technically more difficult and serious complications like retinal detachment, choroidal haemorrhage and endophthalmitis related to transscleral sutures are seen. [4]

Iris claw IOL attached to anterior iris was introduced by Worst in 1972. Major complications associated with it was corneal endothelial damage especially in patients with narrow anterior chamber. Brasse and Neuhann modified this technique by fixing lens to posterior surface of iris, thus preventing endothelial damage.[3]

Primary iris claw implantation means in which IOL implanted in the same sitting after cataract surgery, while secondary iris claw lens implantation is done in post-cataract surgery patients (in second sitting). Because of its peculiar fixation to mid peripheral iris, iris claw implantation can be done in any eye with sufficient iris support. Placement anterior to iris show complications like endothelial decompensation, therefore most surgeons prefer retro-pupillary fixation of iris claw intraocular lens. [1]

In this study we evaluate the post-operative visual acuity and complications after implantation of retro-pupillary iris claw intraocular lens.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective study done at government general hospital, Guntur from May 1st 2023 to April 30th 2024 including 50 eyes of 49 patients. Aphakia secondary to cataract surgery, Intra operative posterior capsule rupture, and zonular dialysis, Stable iris anatomy which allows enclavation of IOL, Normal IOP, and Normal retinal examination were included in this study. The exclusion criteria include uncontrolled glaucoma, Retinal diseases, Iris defects, History of uveitis.

The ethical committee approval was obtained and informed consent was taken from each patient and the study was done according to the declaration of Helsinki.

Preoperatively in all patients detailed history both ocular and medical was taken. General examination of all patients with recording of vital data was done. Complete ocular examination including visual acuity testing with pin hole and best corrected, slit lamp examination, keratometry, A scan, Intraocular pressure recording with Goldmann applanation tonometer, fundus examination with 90D lens and indirect ophthalmoscope, B scan in patients with dense cataracts where fundus cannot be visualised were done.

In our study majority of patients underwent posterior chamber iris claw lens implantation as a

secondary procedure which was done 4 weeks after the first surgery only in 4 patients it was done as a primary procedure. In both cases, patients were given local anaesthesia, superior incision given of size around 6 to 7 mm. In case of secondary surgery opening of previous tunnel with iris repositor was done. Two paracentesis were given at 3 and 9 o'clock positions. Anterior vitrectomy was done. Intracameracarbocbol was used when required. Viscoelastic substance was injected. IOL is inserted into the anterior chamber with haptics in line with the site of paracentesis. Holding the IOL with shepard's IOL holding forceps one haptic is passed beneath the iris on one side and using sinsky's hook the iris is pressed in haptic Loop till depression is noted over the iris. The same is repeated on the other side. Lastly viscoelastic is removed by irrigation and aspiration and anterior chamber is formed. Suturing of wound was done with 10-0 nylon sutures and conjunctiva repositioned. Subconjunctival gentamicin and dexamethasone injection was given and bandage applied. Postoperatively all patients received moxifloxacin and prednisolone eye drops which are tapered over a course of six weeks.

Postoperative visual acuity and complications were noted in all cases.

Results

The study included 50 eyes of 49 patients as one patient underwent bilateral implantation of posterior chamber iris claw lens. Out of 49 patients, 26 were male and 23 were female. Laterality was almost similar with 27 patients in right eye and 23 underwent surgery in left eye. The mean age of patients seen in our study is 56 to 60 years.

Implantation of lens was done as a primary procedure in 4 patients and in 45 it was done as a secondary procedure 4 weeks after first surgery.

Majority of the patients 42 out of 49 in whom iris claw lens implantation done in our study were due to rupture of posterior capsule. In 7 patients zonular dehiscence is the indication for iris claw lens implantation.

The demographic details and indications for iris claw lens implantation in our study were given in table 1.

Most of the patients 20 out of 42 is in range of 6/24 to 6/18. Later at 6weeks follow majority achieved a visual acuity of 6/9 or better.

Postoperative visual acuity is given in figure 1.

In our study complications like striate keratopathy is seen in 26 patients, horizontally oval pupil in 32 and cystoid macular oedema in 2 patients and suprachoroidal haemorrhage in 1 patient. None of our patients develop complications like elevated IOP, retinal detachment.

Figure 2 shows postoperative complications seen in our study.

Figure 1: Immediate post operative Visual Acuity

Figure 2: Post Operative Complications

Table 1:

Demographic details and Indications for Iris claw lens Implantation	
	No. of patients
1. Gender	
Males	26
Females	23
2. Laterality	
Right eye	27
Left eye	23
3. Type of procedure	
Primary	4
Secondary	45
4. Indication	
Posterior capsular rupture	42
Zonular dehiscence	7

Discussion

In cataract surgery one of the complication is posterior capsular rupture leading to difficulty in placement of IOL causing aphakia. Correction of aphakia can be done with help of spectacles, contact lenses and IOL. Spectacle correct of aphakia is associated with decreased peripheral vision, image magnification by 30%, and increased weight of glasses. Therefore, correction of aphakia with IOL implantation can overcome these problems. Among the IOLs anterior chamber, scleral fixating or iris claw lens can be used.

Anterior chamber lens is technically easier but associated with problems of corneal endothelial decompensation, angle trauma with hyphaema, secondary glaucoma. Scleral fixation of IOL has more complications both intraoperatively and postoperatively. A study done by Kumar DA et al observed complications like IOL decentration, haptics extrusion, pigment dispersion and CME. [4]

Iris claw lens can be implanted in anterior chamber and posterior chamber, anterior chamber placement is associated with damage to corneal endothelium. The posterior placement of iris claw lens was introduced by Brasse and Neuhann and this protects the endothelium of corneal. Posterior placement has the advantage of simpler procedure, positioning near nodal point without use of extra sutures. [4]

In our study we took the data of 49 patients who underwent retro-pupillary iris claw lens implantation.

We have collected data regarding preoperative workup done, intraoperative procedure and postoperative follow-up and seen the improvement in visual acuity and postoperative complications.

In our study we have seen an improvement in visual acuity in majority of patients which is similar to a study done by DeSilva et al. [5] other complications like horizontally oval pupil was seen in 32 patients which require no intervention for pupillary distortion. Twenty-six patients with striate keratopathy on post-operative day 1 improved subsequently on follow-ups. No adjuvant medications were required other than topical

antibiotic and steroid drops. This is in comparison to other studies in the literature. CME was seen in 2 patients which resolved with medical management. In our series we have seen only 1 patient with suprachoroidal haemorrhage which was referred to retina specialist which was reduced after treatment. No patient in our study presented with complications like elevated IOP, retinal detachment, spontaneous disenclavation.

The limitation of our study was its relatively small sample size and short follow-up period of only 6 weeks. Larger sample studies and longer follow-up are required to assess the advantages of iris claw lenses and its postoperative complications.

Conclusion

In our study we have demonstrated posterior chamber iris claw lens implantation.

Implantation of posterior chamber iris claw lens is a safe and effective procedure to treat aphakia caused due to inadequate capsular support during cataract surgery. Compared to other methods of correction of aphakia, retro-pupillary iris claw lens has less intraoperative and postoperative complications.

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